

Supporting Information

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I. SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE CAPTIONS (TABLES S1 – S7)

TABLE S1

Complete list of specimens used in this study. The table notes specimen status (i.e., fossil vs. extant), ontogenetic age, and source. Measurements for total mandibular (straight length, SL) and symphyseal length (SY) are included, as well as units (millimeters or pixels) and measurement source (ImageJ or published literature). The table also indicates whether the listed measurements report preserved or estimated lengths. For mysticetes with convex mandibles, chord length (Ch) is reported instead of straight length. Elongation (SY/SL) is calculated for specimens with mandibles complete enough to measure or estimate SL or SY.

TABLE S2

Modifications to tree by Lloyd & Slater (2021). Includes two species substitutions, four updates to taxonomic nomenclature, and 36 additions. For the added taxa, position and branch length are inferred from the primary literature and Paleobiology Database (www.paleobiodb.org). Divergence dates for terrestrial artiodactyls are from Meredith et al. (2011).

TABLE S3

Ecological data used in ecological analyses. Includes data for five ecological traits: (1) feeding strategy, (2) habitat, (3) dive type, (4) prey type, and (5) dentition. The categories and scores for the first five traits follow Coombs et al. (2024). Data for taxa not included in Coombs et al. (2024) were sourced from the primary literature.

TABLE S4

Evolutionary rates for symphyseal fusion across 30 equal-sized time bins. Evolutionary rate is defined as number of shifts divided by total edge length for each bin.

TABLE S5

Evolutionary rates for symphyseal elongation across 30 equal-sized time bins. Evolutionary rate is defined as number of shifts divided by total edge length for each bin.

TABLE S6

Results of Chi-squared tests of independence evaluating the relationship between fusion and ecological variables. Each test was conducted for the total dataset and by group (archaeocetes, odontocetes, and mysticetes). Significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are shaded in yellow. Standard residuals and percent contributions are reported for each test.

TABLE S7

Results of analyses of variance evaluating the relationship between elongation and ecological variables. Each test was conducted for the total dataset and by group (archaeocetes, odontocetes, and mysticetes). Significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are shaded in yellow. Mean elongation values are reported for each test.

II. SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES AND FIGURES

FIGURE S1

Cetacean mandibles exemplifying the four states of symphyseal fusion used in this study. A) State 0: Unfused, freely mobile mandibles characterized by a smooth symphyseal surface. Symphyseal groove = sg. The right mandible of *Balaenoptera acutorostrata* (UWBM 33258) in dorsal view (reflected) and a close-up of the symphyseal surface are shown. B) State 1: Unfused, slightly mobile symphysis defined by a smooth-to-undulatory symphyseal surface. Mandibles of *Phocoenoides dalli* (UWBM 60331) in dorsal view and a close-up of the symphyseal surface are shown. C) State 2: Partially fused, immobile symphysis defined by a rugose symphyseal surface and varying degrees of bony interdigitation. Mandibles of *Globicephala macrorhynchus* (UWBM 35429) in dorsal view and a close-up of the symphyseal surface are shown. D) State 3: Completely fused (ankylosed), immobile symphysis characterized by sutural obliteration. Mandibles of *Platanista gangetica* (USNM VZ 23456) in dorsal view and a close-up of the anteriormost portion of the symphysis are shown.

FIGURE S2

Methodology for measuring mandibles. A) Different measurements historically reported as mandible length for concave (*Saghacetus osiris*), straight (*Tursiops truncatus*), and convex (*Balaenoptera acutorostrata*) mandibles. Diagonal length (DL) and curvilinear length (Cu) are measured along the surface of the mandible, from the anteriormost point of the mandible to the condyle (Pyenson et al., 2013; Werth, 2006). Straight length (SL) is the anteroposterior length of the mandible parallel to the sagittal plane (Nakamura et al., 2013). Chord length (Ch) measures the straight-line distance between anteriormost and posteriormost points of convex mandibles (Field et al., 2010; Pyenson et al., 2013). B) Standardized measurements for mandible length (SL) and symphyseal length (SY) used in this study.

FIGURE S3
ER model for symphyseal fusion. The model assumes equal transition rates between states.

FIGURE S4
SYM model for symphyseal fusion. The model assumes that transition rates between states are symmetric.

FIGURE S5
ARD model for symphyseal fusion. The model allows variable transition rates between states.

FIGURE S6
Marked changes (shifts in fusion state) for one simulated tree.

FIGURE S7
Marked changes (shifts in fusion state) for 100 trees randomly sampled from 1000 simulated trees.

FIGURE S8
Marked changes (shifts in fusion state) for 1000 simulated trees.

FIGURE S9

“Rate-through-time” plot of symphyseal fusion. Rate is defined as number of changes in fusion state divided by total edge length, calculated for each of 30 equal-sized time bins across 1,000 stochastic simulations. Stochastic maps were generated using a fitted model assuming symmetrical transition rates (see Figure S4).

FIGURE S10

Discrete ordered model for symphyseal elongation, fitted using fitHRM. Method follows Revell (2023). The model assumes variable rates between adjacent states. The model captures transitions from state 1 to state 0, but no transitions occur out of state 0.

FIGURE S11
 Marked changes (shifts in elongation state) for 1000 simulated trees.

FIGURE S12
 “Rate-through-time” plot of symphyseal elongation. Rate is defined as number of changes in elongation state divided by total edge length, calculated for each of 30 equal-sized time bins across 1,000 stochastic simulations. Stochastic maps were generated using a fitted ordered model assuming variable transition rates (see Figure S10).

TABLE S8

Results of analysis of variance testing the relationship between symphyseal fusion and elongation. The total dataset (N = 149 taxa) for which this relationship was tested only includes taxa with mandibles complete enough to measure or estimate SY and SL (see Figure S2).

	N	df	F value	p value
Total	149	(3, 145)	74.48	<0.001
Archaeocetes	10	(1, 8)	1.394	0.272
Odontocetes	98	(2, 95)	26.64	<0.001
Mysticetes	37	(2, 34)	56.8	<0.001

FIGURE S13

Distribution of elongation values across fusion states. Elongation (SY/SL) is shown on the y-axis, and categories of fusion (states 0-4) are shown on the x-axis. Letters denote three statistically significant groups: a = state 0, b = state 1 and 2, c = state 3. Shape indicates phylogenetic group: archaeocete, mysticete, odontocete, or terrestrial artiodactyl. Color indicates elongation bin.

FIGURE S14

Distribution of feeding strategies across symphyseal morphology. Elongation (SY/SL) is shown on the y-axis, and fusion states (state 0-4) are shown on the x-axis. Shape indicates phylogenetic group: archaeocete, mysticete, or odontocete. Color indicates feeding strategy: Filter, raptorial, or suction.

FIGURE S15

Distribution of habitat types across symphyseal morphology. Elongation (SY/SL) is shown on the y-axis, and fusion states (state 0-4) are shown on the x-axis. Shape indicates phylogenetic group: archaeocete, mysticete, or odontocete. Color indicates habitat: Riverine, coastal, coastal-pelagic, and pelagic.

FIGURE S16

Distribution of dive types across symphyseal morphology. Elongation (SY/SL) is shown on the y-axis, and fusion states (state 0-4) are shown on the x-axis. Shape indicates phylogenetic group: mysticete or odontocete. Color indicates dive type: Shallow, mid, deep, and very deep.

FIGURE S17

Distribution of dentition types across symphyseal morphology. Elongation (SY/SL) is shown on the y-axis, and fusion states (state 0-4) are shown on the x-axis. Shape indicates phylogenetic group: archaeocete, mysticete, or odontocete. Color indicates dentition: edentulous, homodont, heterodont, or reduced.

FIGURE S18

Distribution of prey types (diet) across symphyseal morphology. Elongation (SY/SL) is shown on the y-axis, and fusion states (state 0-4) are shown on the x-axis. Shape indicates phylogenetic group: archaeocete, mysticete, or odontocete. Color indicates prey type: zooplankton + fish, cephalopods + fish, fish, benthic invertebrates + fish, and tetrapods + fish.

FIGURE S19

Ancestral state reconstruction of symphyseal fusion. Posterior probabilities of ancestral states were estimated using stochastic character mapping. Color indicates fusion state for taxa and ancestral nodes. Major shifts in fusion state are starred. Geologic age is indicated by standardized ICS colors and timescales at the top and bottom of the figure: Paleocene (P), Eocene (E), Oligocene (O), Miocene (M), Pliocene (P), and Quaternary (Q).

FIGURE S20

Ancestral state reconstruction of symphyseal elongation. Elongation (SY/SL) was discretized into five bins, indicated by color. Posterior probabilities of ancestral states were estimated using stochastic character mapping. Geologic age is indicated by standardized ICS colors and timescales at the top and bottom of the figure: Paleocene (P), Eocene (E), Oligocene (O), Miocene (M), Pliocene (P), and Quaternary (Q).

III. REFERENCES

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